

Supporting information to the paper

Pillar, V.D. Trait divergence in plant community assembly is generated by environmental factor interactions, *Journal of Vegetation Science*.

Appendix S1. Additional figures for the introduction of the concept of environmentally-driven trait divergence.

Figure S1. Hypothetical examples showing expected values of trait (t_1) selected (filtered) by one random environmental factor (e_2) or by the interaction of factor e_1 and e_2 , according to specified linear functions. In (a), the simulated trait t_1 is affected by factor e_2 only. In (b) and (c), it is determined by the interaction of factors e_1 and e_2 . The linear function slopes are shown in the insets. The red trendline represents the response of trait t_1 modelled a posteriori with the generated data, using only factor e_1 as a predictor and ignoring factor e_2 and the interaction (greyed in the insets), as if e_2 were not measured. In (a) and (b), the effect of simulated values of factor e_2 on trait t_1 was nested within the nesting factor e_1 . For this, each subset of 10 random values of e_2 in subunits corresponded to one identical random value of e_1 defining a nesting, larger unit. That is, larger, nesting units contained ten subunits that did not vary for e_1 but did for e_2 . In (c), both factors varied randomly across all subunits. Random values were normally-distributed. The corresponding variance of trait t_1 within each of these larger units and its observed response to factor e_1 is shown in graphs d-f.

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Appendix S2. Details on the measuring of environmentally-driven beta trait divergence.

The squared residual v_{ij}^2 of each community i and trait j to beta trait divergence was computed as

$$v_{ij}^2 = (t_{ij} - \hat{t}_{ij})^2$$

Where t_{ij} is the observed and \hat{t}_{ij} is the expected CWM trait value predicted by the one or more environmental factors. It can be demonstrated that v_{ij}^2 is equivalent to the difference between community weighted variance (CWV, Enquist et al., 2015) relative to \hat{t}_{ij} :

$$\sum_h^s p_{ih}(b_{jh} - \hat{t}_{ij})^2$$

and relative to t_{ij} :

$$\sum_h^s p_{ih}(b_{jh} - t_{ij})^2$$

where s is the total number of species in community i , p_{ih} is the proportion of species h in community i , and b_{jh} is the value of trait j for species h .

$$\begin{aligned} v_{ij}^2 &= (t_{ij} - \hat{t}_{ij})^2 = \sum_h^s p_{ih}(b_{jh} - \hat{t}_{ij})^2 - \sum_h^s p_{ih}(b_{jh} - t_{ij})^2 \\ &= \sum_h^s p_{ih}[(b_{jh} - \hat{t}_{ij})^2 - (b_{jh} - t_{ij})^2] \\ &= \sum_h^s p_{ih}[(b_{jh}^2 - 2b_{jh}\hat{t}_{ij} + \hat{t}_{ij}^2) - (b_{jh}^2 - 2b_{jh}t_{ij} + t_{ij}^2)] \\ &= \sum_h^s p_{ih}(b_{jh}^2 - 2b_{jh}\hat{t}_{ij} + \hat{t}_{ij}^2 - b_{jh}^2 + 2b_{jh}t_{ij} - t_{ij}^2) \\ &= -2\hat{t}_{ij} \sum_h^s p_{ih}b_{jh} + \hat{t}_{ij}^2 \sum_h^s p_{ih} + 2t_{ij} \sum_h^s p_{ih}b_{jh} - t_{ij}^2 \sum_h^s p_{ih} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Since } t_{ij} = \sum_h^s p_{ih}b_{jh} \text{ and } \sum_h^s p_{ih} = 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= -2\hat{t}_{ij}t_{ij} + \hat{t}_{ij}^2 + 2t_{ij}t_{ij} - t_{ij}^2 \\ &= \hat{t}_{ij}^2 - 2\hat{t}_{ij}t_{ij} + 2t_{ij}^2 - t_{ij}^2 \\ &= \hat{t}_{ij}^2 - 2\hat{t}_{ij}t_{ij} + t_{ij}^2 \\ &= (\hat{t}_{ij} - t_{ij})^2 = (t_{ij} - \hat{t}_{ij})^2 \end{aligned}$$

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Appendix S3. Brief description of the stochastic, individual-based, spatially explicit metacommunity simulation model.

As depicted in the flowchart (Figure S3), the input for the metacommunity simulation model includes the species pool described by traits and parameters for propagule dispersal and trait-based survival (Fig. 3), as well includes the sites described by environmental factors and mapped geographically.

The community assembly process is iterative. Propagules of the species are dispersed to sites based on a dispersal probability calculated using the distance from the source sites with the same species in the metacommunity. The dispersal probability is defined by a species-specific logistic function, similarly to the trait-based survival. Individual establishment at the site depends on the species' traits and survival probabilities. Survival incorporates density dependent mortality probability, which is specific to each species and is proportional to the ratio between the current number of individuals and the maximum specified for each community. This density-dependent mortality is also defined by the parameters of a logistic function, similar to trait-based survival and dispersal.

The colonisation and death of individuals are repeated multiple times and for all sites until saturation in the number of individuals in the communities is reached. Finally, the simulated species composition data, together with the species traits and the final state of the environmental factors, are analysed to evaluate environmentally-driven alpha and beta trait divergence.

In the case of environmentally driven survival, as illustrated in Figure 3b in the main text, the probabilities are determined by the similarity between the individual and the expected community-weighted mean (CWM) trait, for each trait. The expected CWM in turn is determined by the environmental factor values at the site, based on specified linear response parameters for environmental filtering.

Figure S3. Flowchart of the metacommunity simulation model. The connectors in red represent environmental filtering, and those in blue represent feedback from community to environmental factors. Propagule dispersal is represented by the orange links, while the green ones are related to age and density-dependent survival. The final result is a metacommunity matrix of species composition and, in the case of non-zero feedback parameters, modified environmental factors.

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Appendix S4. Parameters set for the simulation of metacommunities under scenarios A and B, used for the analyses shown in Figures 4 and 5 in the main text.

In (a) the parameters specify the levels of environmental filtering, i.e., community responses to ecosystem conditions and their interaction that were fixed with different values within the indicated ranges for Type I and power evaluations of the correlations $r(\mathbf{RE})$ and $r(\mathbf{VE})$. In (b) the parameters varied randomly within the specified ranges and were not relevant for Type I and power evaluations. In (c) explanations are provided.

(a) Parameters set within the indicated ranges for evaluating Type I error and power of $r(\mathbf{RE})$ and $r(\mathbf{VE})$:

Parameters for linear models of community responses to ecosystem conditions (3 traits by 2 ecosystem predictor variables, and their interaction):

	e_1	e_2	$e_1 \times e_2$
t_1	0 to 0.6	0	0 to 0.6
t_2	0	-0.3	0
t_n	0	0	0

Parameters for linear models of the community feedback effects on ecosystem conditions (2 ecosystem variables by 3 predictor traits):

Scenario A: All the linear coefficients were set to zero.

Scenario B:

0	0	0
0.3	0	0

(b) Parameters that were either fixed or varied randomly within the indicated ranges for every simulated metacommunity irrespective of the settings in (a). Parameters that varied randomly ensured diverse responses among species within the simulated species pool:

<i>Parameters set per metacommunity:</i>	<i>Fixed</i>	<i>Min.</i>	<i>Max.</i>
Number of species in the species pool	150		
Number of communities in the metacommunity (located systematically in a 36 x 36 grid, see Figure S4)	1296		
Expected correlation level between traits in simulated species by traits matrix	0		
Expected correlation level between environmental factors in simulated environmental data matrix (normal distribution)	0		
Spatial autocorrelation, number of cells in adjacent rows (or columns) in the simulated grid taking identical values (see Figure S4): Factor 1: Factor 2:	4 1		
Maximum average number of individuals per community	100		
Number of iterations (cycles of colonization and extinction) per year	50		
Duration of the simulation (years)	100		
<i>Parameters set per species and metacommunity:</i>		<i>Min.</i>	<i>Max.</i>
Centre of antisymmetry of the logistic function for the dispersal kernel		0.1	0.9

Negative slope of the logistic function for the dispersal kernel		-5	-2
Centre of antisymmetry of the logistic function for survival probability		0.1	0.4
Negative slope of the logistic function for survival probability		-5	-2
Centre of antisymmetry of the logistic function for age-related survivorship curves		0.1	0.9
Negative slope of the logistic function for age-related survivorship curve		-5	-2
Centre of antisymmetry of the logistic function for density dependence		0.6	0.9
Negative slope of the logistic function for density dependence		-5	-2
Lifespan of individuals		1	50
Centre of antisymmetry of the logistic function for site inertia probability against community feedback effect		0.1	0.9
Negative slope of the logistic function for site inertia probability against community feedback effect		-5	-2
<i>Parameters set per species, trait and metacommunity:</i>		<i>Min.</i>	<i>Max.</i>
Centre of antisymmetry of the logistic function for survival probability		0.1	0.4
Negative slope of the logistic function for survival probability		-5	-2

(c) *Modus operandi*

Each simulated metacommunity generated a matrix of species traits with an expected zero correlation between traits, and a matrix of community sites with randomly uncorrelated environmental factors. The sites were systematically located on a 36 x 36 grid, and simulated values for the environmental factors were drawn from a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and variance of 1. The values for factor e1 were identical for each set of 16 sites (4 rows x 4 columns) mapped onto the grid (Figure S4), while the values for factor e2 were randomly assigned without spatial restrictions across the 1296 grid sites (scenario A) or were initialized to zero (scenario B).

As described in Appendix S3, species colonization and extinction events were defined based on the probabilities of individuals arriving, establishing, and dying at each community site. These probabilities were all determined by a logistic function with centre and slope parameters set randomly for each simulated species within specified ranges. For propagule arrival, the probability of each species at each site was a function of the spatial distance, normalized to a maximum value of one, between the target community site and every other site in the metacommunity where the same species had successfully established. The dispersal of a given species to a target site was considered successful when at least one propagule of the species arrived. These probabilities were updated annually during the simulation process.

In the case of environmentally driven survival, as illustrated in Figure 3b in the main text, the probabilities were determined by the similarity between the individual and the expected community-weighted mean (CWM) trait for each trait. The expected CWM in turn was determined by the environmental factor values at the site, based on the specified linear response parameters for environmental filtering.

For density-dependent survival and mortality, the probabilities depended on the current total abundance of individuals relative to the maximum predetermined number of individuals in the community. Additionally, for age-related mortality, the probabilities were determined by

the individual's age relative to the species' expected longevity, which was randomly set within the specified range.

In simulation scenario B, the feedback effect from the developing community to environmental factor e2 was applied at each site annually. For this purpose, the annual change in the CWM trait values was computed. This change was then multiplied to the specified linear coefficient for the feedback of trait t1 on e2, in order to predict the annual change in factor e2. The changes at each site and the maximum absolute change across sites were then used in the logistic function to determine the inertia probability for each site. This probability was subsequently multiplied to the predicted change and added the previous year's value of e2 at the site.

After 100 years with 50 cycles of individual colonization and death per year, the simulated metacommunity data was analysed, and the trait divergence patterns compared to the expected ones.

Figure S4. Site locations on a 36 x 36 grid. The values for factor e1 (depicted as shades of grey) were identical for each set of 16 sites (4 rows x 4 columns) mapped onto the grid. The values for factor e2 (depicted as sizes) were randomly assigned without spatial restrictions across the 1296 grid sites for scenario A. For scenario B (not shown), the values for factor e2 were initialized to zero.

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Appendix S5. Sampling design used for the description of species composition and environmental variables in grassland plots across south Brazil.

Figure S5. Sampling design used for the description of species composition and environmental variables in grassland plots across south Brazil. Adapted from (Menezes et al., 2022). The sampling was nested, with sites of 5 x 5 km selected at the regional scale to represent different ecological system types across 6 degrees of latitude. Within the sites, 250-m long, contour transects were marked, and within each transect 10 plots of 1 m x 1 m were surveyed for species composition. Soil was described at the transect level, while the variables total vegetation cover, dung cover and rock cover were visually estimated at the plot level. The present analysis considered the data collected at 11 sites (plots from coastal grasslands were not included), totalling 990 1 m² plots with species presence-absence and the other environmental variables. Soil was described for texture (% of clay, coarse sand, fine sand and silt), organic matter content, pH, nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, aluminium, calcium and magnesium contents, cation exchange capacity, base saturation and aluminium saturation.

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Appendix S6. Environmentally-driven trait divergence detected in simulated metacommunity data, including plots with cases of data generated for different combinations of parameters.

(a)

(b)

Figure S6. Environmentally-driven trait divergence detected in simulated metacommunity data considering the specified combinations of parameters using scenario A in (a) and scenario B in (b). These results are the same as those shown in Figures 4 and 5 in the main text but now include plots with cases of data generated for different combinations of parameters. The plots illustrate the effect of factor e1 on CWM trait t1, and in one case, the effect of factor e1 on CWM trait t2.

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Appendix S7. Simulation results considering the specified combinations of parameters under scenarios A and B (Figures 4a and 5a in the main text), but using first-order linear regression to compute the residuals \mathbf{V} to measure beta trait divergence by the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$.

(a)

(b)

Figure S7. Environmentally-driven beta trait divergence detected in simulated metacommunity data considering the specified combinations of parameters under scenarios A (a) and B (b), but beta trait divergence $r(\mathbf{VE})$ was measured using first-order linear regression to compute the residuals in \mathbf{V} . Similar to Figures 4 and 5 in the main text, each graph in both panels depicts the proportions of significant beta trait divergence measured by the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$, with increasing linear coefficients for the effect of the interaction between environmental factors e_1 and e_2 on trait t_1 , as built into the simulation. The rows refer to the scale of the community units, indicating whether the analysis considered the 1296 communities without pooling or with adjacent communities pooled into 81 communities. The effects of the other factor remained constant in every simulation. Trait t_n involved no selection effects. The red lines correspond to trait t_1 , while the other lines represent traits t_2 and t_n . Trait divergence is not expected in the absence of factor interaction; thus the proportion of significant trait divergence indicates Type I error, while for non-zero interaction, it indicates the power of the permutation test for $r(\mathbf{VE})$. Each proportion was determined after 100 simulations for each specified combination of parameters.

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Appendix S8. Simulation results considering a slight variation of the specified combinations of parameters under scenario A (Figure 4a in the main text), incorporating an additional filtering factor, e_1 squared.

(a)

Factor effects on traits:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 e_1 \xrightarrow{0 \text{ to } 0.6} \text{Trait } t_1 \xleftarrow{-0.3} e_1^2 \\
 e_1 \times e_2 \xrightarrow{0 \text{ to } 0.6} \\
 e_2 \xrightarrow{-0.3} \text{Trait } t_2
 \end{array}$$

(b)

(c)

Figure S8. Environmentally-driven beta trait divergence detected in simulated metacommunity data considering a slight variation of the specified combinations of parameters under scenario A (Figure 4a in the main text). In this variation, an additional factor e_1 squared was included as filtering factor on trait t_1 , as shown in (a). In (b), beta trait divergence, measured by the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$, used a second-order polynomial regression to compute the residuals \mathbf{V} , while in (c), it used a first-order linear regression. Plots depicting data generated for different combinations of parameters are presented. Similar to Figure 4a in the main text, each graph shows the proportions of significant beta trait divergence measured by the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$, with increasing linear coefficients for the effect of the interaction between environmental factors e_1 and e_2 on trait t_1 , as built into the simulation. The analysis considered the 1296 communities without pooling. The effects of the squared factor e_1 and the other factors remained constant in every simulation. Trait t_n involved no selection effects. The red lines correspond to trait t_1 , while the other lines represent traits t_2 and t_n . Trait divergence is not expected in the absence of factor interaction; thus the proportion of significant trait divergence indicates Type I error, while for non-zero interaction, it reflects the power of the permutation test for $r(\mathbf{VE})$. Each proportion was found after 100 simulations for each specified combination of parameters.

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Appendix S9. Principal coordinates analysis based on Beals transformed species composition of grassland plots.

Figure S9. Principal coordinates analysis based on Beals transformed species composition of 990 1-m² grassland plots, described by presence-absence of 743 species. In this ordination diagram the plots corresponding to each ecosystem type (see Figure S5) are identified by the same colour. The green dots are highland grasslands. Traits (specific leaf SLA, LDMC, LeafN and LA) aggregated at the community level (CWM) are plotted according to their correlation with the ordination axes. We can visualize trait convergence by projecting the community mean traits based on their correlations with the ordination axes of the Beals transformed species composition. Soil variables are also projected on the ordination. The soil variables are represented by the first two principal components axes of the soil data, one mostly reflecting soil aluminium, and the other soil calcium.